

Teenage Motherhood: Challenges and Solutions in a Digital Environment

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the social and psychological implications of teenage motherhood in selected areas of Lagos State and explore the importance of technology in alleviating the myriads of challenges faced by teenage mothers. Specifically, the study sought to determine whether or not teenage mothers experience psychological distress during pregnancy and nursing, and to explore the nature of such distress. Twenty five (25) teenage mothers were conveniently sampled to participate in the study. Their ages ranged from 13 to 20 years, with the nursing period ranging from 3 months to 5 years. The sample included teenage mothers from uneducated, high schools and tertiary institutions in Ajeromi-Ifelodun (Ajegunle) and Ojo (Oto/Ijanikin) Local Government Areas of Lagos State. Data was collected using qualitative method which involved three focus group interviews conducted with the participants. The first group was not exposed to digital services, the second group was partially exposed to technology while the third group was well exposed to the social media/digital services and was able to access social, economic, emotional and psychological supports. The results showed psychological trauma during pregnancy and nursing periods for most of them. They were also found to experience anxiety, fear, social isolation and frustration as they tried to cope with the demands of motherhood. The study further discovered that teen mothers struggled with disbelief of being pregnant and the reality of being a mother and this psychological frame of mind causes depression that more often than not result in attempted suicide. Based on the findings, it was discovered that participants without exposure to digital services experienced serious psychological trauma, shame, hopelessness and rejection compared to participants with minimal and full exposure to digital services wherein they were able to access social, economic and emotional help. The findings agree with previous researches that teenage motherhood comes with a lot of social, psychological and emotional trauma such as depression, insomnia, diminishing self-esteem, abortion and ultimately attempted suicide. The study, therefore, recommends that more sex and reproductive education must be encouraged in both primary and secondary levels of education. Government and Non-governmental Organizations must partner with welfare groups to provide necessary socio-economic supports for the teenage mother such that will guarantee her re-entry and continuation of her education.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Psychological distress, Social isolation, Teenage mother.

Introduction

Teenage motherhood is the circumstance in which teenagers from the age of 13 to 19 get pregnant and become mothers. Motherhood in itself is a thing of pride in Africa as it is in many parts of the world. The process of becoming a mother also varies with culture across the world. In some climes, especially among the Yorubas of West Africa, a woman is expected to be “initiated” into the realm of motherhood by certain conditions that she must meet because motherhood is not known to be for teenagers. Therefore there are rites of engagement which must be performed through demands from the groom’s parents certain traditional elements, one of which is the bride price. These obligations must be met before marriage is consummated between two adults. So, just as marriage is not for boys/girls, motherhood is also not for boys or girls because of some conditions attached to it. Traditionally, teenagers are not expected to go into marriage let alone become a mother and that explains why motherhood for teenagers becomes a serious challenge when it advertently or inadvertently happens.

Teenage pregnancy and motherhood are two stages identified in teenager's social life in this study. While teenage pregnancy describes a situation where a teenager is put in a family way either intentionally or accidentally, teenage motherhood denotes teenager in circumstance of a nursing mother. It is believed that one stage leads to the other in most cases, but not all the time, because of the option of abortion. The first stage which is teenage pregnancy, the teenager carries pregnancy in her womb, legally or illegally depending on the culture of the environment for at least nine months. The stage comes with its own social, psychological, emotional and economic challenges which the teenager has to deal with. Here, the issue of acceptability of the reality on the part of the pregnant teenager, the acceptability of responsibility for the child by the father, most often male teens, and consideration of abortion as a solution to the challenge. The second stage is the teenage motherhood, a social condition in which a teenager becomes a mother. This presupposes that the teenage girl has decided willingly to keep the pregnancy and eventually delivered the baby. The moment she delivers the baby, the teenage girl becomes a mother hence begins to deal with the challenges associated with nursing a baby. These challenges also range from acceptability of the baby from the father, responsibility and care for the welfare of the baby, emotional trauma and sometimes health risk such as fistula. That is why emphasis is on how efforts will be geared towards providing teenagers in this circumstance with the necessary help and services that will help them grow and overcome (Stephen et al 2003). The understanding of the two stages will help in distinguishing the kind of support needed at each stage of the experience. Most studies have tended to treat the two as two in one. They give the impression that teenage pregnancy is synonymous with teenage motherhood.

However, it must be stated that both teenage pregnancy and motherhood give cause for concern in African sub region and developed world. Catherine B, Jonah NK & Joseph K.L (2014) opine that:

Teenage pregnancy and teenage motherhood is a concern in both developed and developing countries and is a complex reality of contemporary society, however the re-entry of teenage mother into the school systems continue to demand attention as society’s negative attitude towards pregnant girls and teenage mothers persist.p.1

Studies have confirmed that the challenge of teenage motherhood is not limited to underdeveloped countries although it may have higher percentage because of the quality of life offered by poor nations. For instance, Karen Robson and Richard Berthould (2003) believed that in western countries, the age range during which women are conventionally assumed to be fertile is between

age 14 and 44. So a high percentage of babies are born when their parents are between 20s and 30s. Accordingly:

Relatively few women conceive and give birth before the age of 20. Teenage motherhood is increasingly rare in many countries, mainly because prolonged education, increased employment opportunities and the availability of contraception has tended to delay a woman's decision to start a family. p.451

It is a global challenge with its attendant negative consequences both in developed and less developed countries of the world (Treffer, 2003), (Lucker, 2010). Close to 16million girls become pregnant annually worldwide according to World Health Organization (WHO2011).

The attempt by researchers to justify low occurrence of teenage motherhood in countries with employment opportunities, prolonged education and availability of contraception is slightly flawed by the conjecture that those factors delay a woman's decision to start a family. The truth is that in both developed and less developed countries, teenage pregnancy and motherhood are mostly unplanned and unprepared for. That explains why most teenage mothers contend with the rejection and emotional trauma that come with such experience. In fact, Catherine et al (2014), Treffer (2003) believe "Teenage motherhood is a global phenomenon affecting both developed and developing countries."p.1. Of course, it cannot be denied that there is prevalence of teenage motherhood in developing/less developed countries, especially Sub-Saharan Africa, the reason is not far from corruption and bad governmental policy that make education of the girl child difficult. For instance, some countries in Sub-Saharan Africa do not prioritize education for the girl child as a lot of girls are still denied access to education especially when they are pregnant or become teen mothers (Meena2001). Another reason is also the fact that teenagers between the age of 14 to 19 are sexually active and are ready to explore in their youthful stage thus making them highly vulnerable.

There is no doubt the fact that this is the reality among Nigerian youths today and this situation comes with its own challenges ranging from premature death arising from abortion, bareness due to repeated abortion, detrimental health hazard during childbearing, fistula, girl child dropout of school, poor child care, rejection and diminishing self-esteem. According to Bamao-Kiptanui et al (2014), "Teenage mothers face many challenges trying to complete their schooling because over and above their academic work, just like their peers, they are mothers first. p.63

The teenage mother is faced, first and foremost, with the challenge of dropping out of school no matter how brilliant. She is considered to have taken the option of truncating her education by her pregnancy and subsequently, motherhood. Either willingly or otherwise, conditions of motherhood will not give her room to actively participate in her education. According to Chilisia,(2002), a teenage mother is faced with three problems even at pregnancy – expulsion, the possibility of re-entry and continuation of her education. Each problem comes with serious challenges. For instance, the moment a school girl is pregnant, she is automatically expelled or she expels herself; after nursing her baby, it is difficult for her to be reintegrated because of rejection and poor educational policy; to continue her education is as difficult as re-entry because of the added responsibility of caring for her baby and paying school fees. The expulsion policy in some African countries has been roundly criticized as a lopsided policy that violates the right of the teenage mother expelled while the father is left to continue his education. For the policy to have its full merit, if any, the

father should be made to stop school until the child is delivered. According to Barmao-Kiptanui et al (2014):

The expulsion policy has further been specifically criticized as one that is insensitive to the needs of the girl and that it tends to bracket the reasons for teenage pregnancy as a girl's problem and fear to look at factors that leads to her getting pregnant before completing her education. p.63

This is, apart from the fact that the teenage mother's welfare has been largely neglected during pregnancy up until she gives birth and only have to nurture her alone without any provision or support from government. They are denied education immediately they become pregnant or as teen mothers. Some schools in African countries disallow pregnant teens and teen mothers from attending classes (Wolpe et al, (1997), while those who resume school after nursing their children are considered weak intellectually (Pillow, 2004). In fact, Shultz (2001), opines that pregnancy during school provides grounds for staff and the teen's families to abandon them and their education. Poverty is another very serious challenge the teenage mother is confronted with. More often than not, poor social condition is responsible for teen pregnancy in situation where parents are unable to provide for the needs of their teen girls. Some of them become vulnerable to rich men who take advantage of their poor condition to provide their needs in exchange for sex. Hunter and May (2003), cited by Barmao-Kiptanui *et al* (2014) insist "poverty is a plausible explanation of school disruption for the majority of girls who dropped out of school in Zambia". p.63. Levies and school fees charged by schools further put teenage school girls under financial pressure before and after pregnancy (Nwansa et al, 2004).

Cultural practices in some counties in Sub-Saharan Africa encourage young girls to get married early. For instance, in northern Nigeria where the education of the girl child is still a huge challenge, teenagers easily get married to elderly men with little regard for their age. Such teenage mothers are either abandoned or kept incommunicado under *pudah* system (Eleha) that makes re-entry or continuation of schooling a piped drum.

Lack of access to technology is a great challenge to the teen mother whose lifeline and support may just be information to somewhere on the internet. Some teenage mothers interviewed in this study do not have access to the internet, zero knowledge of technology, can barely operate an android phone and bereft of any knowledge of information super highway. Most of the support the teenage mother access are mainly those provided by their parents and members of their families, while majority of them do not have access to digital support through digital services emails, chats, mobile apps, social media, twitter, instagram, we-chat, whatsapp and telegram among others that could help them take advantage of online support critically needed.

Theoretical Framework

Feminism is the struggle for the emancipation of women from the stranglehold of age-long patriarchal ideals that hold them down. It is a theory that seeks a fundamental change in gender relations in a way that recognizes and appreciates the value of women as active member of a human society. The drive in feminist struggle is for equity and equality in a world dominated by men. Feminism, therefore, struggles to rewrite women narratives from the point of view of the women who experience firsthand deprivation and exclusion in the way the society is organized.. Proponents of feminism or its adherents try to project the positive contribution of the women folk in the process of advancing the society for the betterment of both men and women in all spheres of

human endeavors. This struggle cut across all fields, medicine, politics, history, science, economics, music and literature, among other professions. Feminism provides a platform for women not only to assert themselves but to free themselves from what Mary Wollstonecraft describes as “assumptions that allows people to make jokes and cause women to hide their creativity” (Dobie, 2009: 105). Wollstonecraft in *A Vindication of the Rights of Women* cited in (Dobie, 2009) argues that women should be:

...Duly prepared by education to be the "companions of men" and called for the members of her sex to take charge of their lives by recognizing that their abilities were equal to those of men, to define identities for themselves, and to carve out their own roles in the society. p.106.

In literature, especially creative enterprise, feminist decries the unjust depiction of women by male writers. The frown at the stereotypical portraiture of women as talkative, weak, gossipers, sex objects, witchcraft, and such other negative stereotypes in men's creative outputs. Olutoyin Jegede (2009) says “portraits which demean the importance, value and intelligence of women, shape the readers' ideas of what it means to be male and female in the society.” p.261. Feminist put women issues on the front burner and are committed to their liberation from all forms of oppression. Women advocacy centers on making men to create space for women, and challenge denial of women's right to opportunities in the society.

For a better understanding of the framework of this study, feminist ideology is narrowed down to 'Motherism,' an African strand of feminism propounded by Acholonu.C.O. (1995:110-111) where she contends that as an alternative to feminism, "motherism denotes motherhood, nature and nurture."p.111.

According to her:

An Afrocentric feminist theory, therefore must be anchored on the matrix of motherhood which is central to African metaphysics and has the basis of survival and unity of the black race through ages. Whatever Africa's role may be in the global perspective, it could never be divorced from her quintessential position as the mother of humanity, nor is it coincidental that motherhood has remained the central focus of African art, African Literature...p.110-111

Motherhood from Acholonu's stand point is central to African female experience. It presupposes that the mother is a symbol of "self-sacrificing love, endurance, nurture, provider of warmth among other virtues"(Sotunsa M.E & Yacob-Haliso. O. 2012:88). Although the roles women are projected positively in feminist ideals, it is better captured in motherism because Africa is family centred and the mother is at the heart of the family unit. However, Motherism has been demystified by African writers and critics who believe that the concept is not good enough as representative of the fulfilling role of the African woman if the bitter experiences associated with motherhood in some creative works like Nwanpa's *Joy of Motherhood* (1979) is anything to go by. In this study, however, this contrary opinion is, indeed, considered an enrichment of motherhood for its capacity to unmask the hidden intricacies underpinning the concept.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion

This study employs qualitative approach which involved interviews of three focus groups. The interviews investigated experiences of teenage mothers during pregnancy and as teen mothers. They also shared what it means to be a teen mother, the emotional, psychological, socio-economic and diminishing self esteem associated with the condition of teen motherhood. The teen mothers interviewed were assigned codes in order to protect their identities in line with the promise made to use information provided in confidence. The following codes were used: TMAO1, TMAO2, TMAO3, TMAO4, TMAO5, TMAO6, TMAO7, TMAO8, TMAO9, TMAO10. The codes generated are representatives of the subject matter of the discourse, location and number assigned to each participant. Out of the twenty five participants, eleven were forthcoming and gave useful information while fourteen (14) did not supply responses relevant to the research. The codes denotes:

T=Teenage

M=Mother

A=Ajeromi/Ifelodun

O=Ojo

The teenage mothers who participated in the focus group are between 14 and 19 years of age, majorly drop out of school and uneducated few. The nursing period also ranges from three (3) months to five (5) years. It must be noted that not all of them have access to digital services and so were disadvantaged while those exposed to technology made maximum use of it for self-sufficiency. The three focus groups who participated in the study were assisted by a philanthropist who has been in touch with teen mothers but chose to remain anonymous. The first group was not exposed to digital technology, the second group was partially exposed while the third group was well exposed to digital technology and services, hence were able to access support. Some of the participants chose not to supply information about some personal details which was respected. The interviews were largely conducted in Yoruba and pidgin and translated to English after they were transcribed. Only very few of the twenty five participants spoke in English. Emphasis was on confidentiality which the study did not compromise.

TMAO1: *I am now 19 years of age. I got pregnant when I was 15 plus and couldn't continue my education. From pregnancy to delivery, I saw hell. All my friends abandoned me, including my parents. I didn't know I would survive it. My android phone that my boyfriend bought for me when we met became my friend. I will sometimes go to the internet and post my pictures and some terrible words just to console myself. Some comments are annoying while some are encouraging. At times, I meet friends who do not know I already have a baby, and they helped me ease tension especially when I am down and think of suicide or killing the baby, or the two of us all together. A friend sent an empowerment programme to me on whatsapp and they said we should register with 15,000. Initially, I thought it was one those 419 people. Though I didn't even have the money. But thanks to my friend's sister who paid for me. I finished both the online training and I think they are saying they will give us small loan. I don't know true oo.*

At 16 plus years of age motherhood to TMAO1 was traumatic. She narrated her frustration and rejection by those close to her; her parents and friends. her major challenge was dealing with rejection and loneliness which at times led to consideration of suicide or attempt to kill the baby. For her parents to abandon her, at a time when she needed support during pregnancy and childbirth could be traumatizing. So, from pregnancy to motherhood, she has faced the challenges of

abandonment, rejection, fear, attempted suicide and hopelessness coupled with disruption of in education.

TMAO2: *I was a little above 14 years. I was able to learn how to tie gele and do make up online. Since my baby is still young, I couldn't leave her at home to go and learn work and I need to empower myself. You know I dropped out of school in SS2. One of my sisters paid for me because everybody abandoned me. Nothing can be more frustrating. People look at you as if you rubbed Shit on your body. Like a leper or a thief. As in... you cry your heart out. Even the baby you are not able to carry him out. At times I would have dressed for my baby with nice cloth but to carry him out, is a big shame. I thank God, six months into the online apprenticeship, I already have clients who will call for home service and some people who know me in my neighborhood also patronize me. I will be alright.*

16-year-old TMAO2 dropped out of school at SS2 level and as such could not continue her education. she experienced diminishing self-esteem and frustration from people's reaction to her pregnancy and her motherhood status. The pride of motherhood is lost on the strength of contemptuous look on the faces of those who she met as pregnant teenager and as teen mother. She says "people look at you as if you rub shit on your body." At times, I would have dressed for my baby with nice cloth but to carry him out is a big shame". This experience is burn out of the social condition attached to pregnancy and motherhood which are believed to be exclusive preserve of married adults not teenagers.

TMAO3: *I was 15 years old when I became a mother. I don't want to recount my experiences. Nobody will want to even listen to you. You could still enjoy love, care from people before your pregnancy is visible but the moment they know you are pregnant, hostilities begin, even from my very close friend. I learnt photography. Ha, those years were terrible years for me. No friend, no husband, no parents, no money. Even to browse the internet, no data. Any time I am able to buy data, my spirit come alive. Once in a while... Until I was introduced to photography, and my boss was really compassionate. In fact, I will say he trained me free of charge. So it is the little income from the money I make from being a job man with my Oga that I use in taking care of myself. I would have loved to be on my own but to buy good digital camera, you must have like 200,000. That is a used Tokunbo with clear picture.*

Describes the nine months of pregnancy with the period of nurturing the baby after childbirth as terrible. She also faced rejection from those who supposed to provide the needed support. She says: "No friend, no parents, no money." Usually, pregnant teens or teen mothers always secure the support their mothers emotionally and financially, but in her own situation, such supports were not forthcoming which means she had to fend for herself and her baby in the face of harsh economic situation.

TMAO4: *My husband people set me up with a small business centre in a campus of a higher institution. So I was forced to learn computer so I can manage the shop. It was complete with color printer, black and white printer, a photocopier and a small camera for passport photograph. I was really empowered because my husband is still in the university, 300 level. He will finish next year. So I am able to take care of myself, my baby and even buy some stuff for my husband in school. No. I have never contemplated suicide, but at times the way some people look at you as if you are a small girl with a baby makes me ashamed. And you know my husband is not usually around. I finished SSS3 with a good result. I am just 17. I will still go back to school when my husband finishes from university. I cannot be a drop out.*

TMAO4 received support from her in-laws who set her up in business. Although a teenager, pregnancy was not a difficult condition for her because her undergraduate husband was a pillar of financial, emotional and social support. Motherhood was to her a thing of pride because she was supported and empowered. She says "No, I have never contemplated suicide." She, however, claims to have experienced uncomplimentary stare from people who look at her with perception that seems to pass a negative comment about her as a teen mother.

TMAO5: *I was just a little above 14 years, in JSS3 when I became a mother. Ha, people talked to me like. I don't want to think about it. I was ashamed of going out and that was why I did not go for antenatal until I was seven even eight months pregnant. The nurses call you Iya oloyun, and the way some people looked at you. I was lucky I met somebody who told me about an empowerment program, I enrolled for digital photography and editing. I am still doing it even with my little baby. Delivery was difficult but I was forced to push when they told me it might result to death, stillbirth or cesarean operation. Heen, where is the money? If not for my mum, who pardoned me after she became very angry because of the pregnancy. To drop out of school is not good. I will still go back to school but I want to become the best photographer in the world.*

Just a little above 14 years when she became a mother, TMAO5 dropped out of school in JSS3. She experienced diminishing self-esteem, rejection and shame arising from negative comments by those who saw her condition as social aberration. "I was ashamed of going out and that was why I did not go for antenatal until I was seven, even eight months pregnant." Psychological trauma came about as a result of rejection from her mum who ordinarily would have supported her. Until her mother forgave and her accepted her back, she was an outcast. However, she became hopeful when the mother pardoned her, in fact only then was she able to go back to school.

TMAO6: *At 15 years, I was infatuated, let me say raped because it was not what I bargained for. Although he was my boy friend. I had no idea what pregnancy was, until a friend asked me some questions like when last did you see your period. I was merely treating malaria. I thought the world was collapsing on me. Twice I considered suicide. Even after I delivered the baby it feels like I should throw her away. The shame of pregnancy was serious. You don't want to be pregnant like that. I couldn't wait to greet my class mates. I was referred to as old woman, that alone...Help eventually came through a family member who gave me a link that referred me to an empowerment organization that gave me and my baby support and trained me. I don't want to mention their name...*

TMAO6 was fifteen when she became pregnant, and was totally oblivious of such experience until her friend enlightened her. Sex education and ignorance of reproductive knowledge become obvious in her experience. So instead of confiding in her mother who, of course is more experienced, she chose to confide in her friend. Frustration set in, as a result of shame arising from the perception of people who viewed her condition with contempt. For her to contemplate suicide suggests a difficult state of affairs which she needed to contend with until help came. It is the same sense of rejection, lack of help, psychological and emotional trauma that combined to define her response and adjustment to the reality of motherhood. The hope of going back to school for TMAO6 is slim.

TMAO7: *I don't want to talk about it. Hmmm. For months, I couldn't sleep and when I did, I would be woken up by bad dream. I cannot tell how many times I have attempted abortion and it failed. Up till now I have not recovered. See the baby. The father is nowhere....I cannot feed him.*

No work. Who will employ a nursing mother? Since I got pregnant I have not been able to continue my casual job because we stand throughout the day.

The experience of TMAO7 is one of abandonment, insomnia and depression since those who supposed to provide emotional support have deserted her. There is a state of disbelief and fear that she was actually becoming a mother. Obviously she was not psychologically and emotionally prepared for the ordeal of pregnancy and motherhood as a teenager. For her, the challenges are not just abandonment and fear but the problem of caring for herself and the baby. She says " See the baby, I cannot feed him." Research has proven that 70% financial and emotional supports will come from mothers of teenage mothers and close associates such as sisters and the husband or would-be father. It is when these psychosocial and emotional supports are in short supply that emotional stress and depression set in.

TMAO8: *My pregnancy was not a mistake, he deceived me into it. It was our plan to have the baby before I gained admission. I took the decision on my own. In fact, my parents were disappointed, even up till now they can still not believe I could do such a thing. To make matter worse for me, he started misbehaving few months to my delivery. He came to name the child and has since disappeared. Shame, of course that he is not there. Frustration because the load is on me. Since I missed the admission year, I am learning computer programming, computer graphics and even repairs in a private computer center. That is my only consolation. I am not sure I can still go back to school because I am the only one taking care of my boy and myself.*

This participant seemed to ignorantly prepare for motherhood out of infatuation and not because she knew what she was going into. She envisaged a tomorrow she was not sure of in spite of her decision to face it. May be TMAO8 would not have experienced the frustration and shame that came with her condition if the father of the child has not disappeared after naming the child. Hers is a case of frustration, abandonment, shame and socio-economic challenge. The initial disappointment by her parents obviously has eroded trust and ultimately filial support due largely to disruption of her education caused by pregnancy.

TMAO9: *I cannot explain the frustration. I disappointed my dad. My mum is no more. So I was sent to the village in Ondo State. It was when my baby was 2 years that they begged my dad to take me back. Nobody to complain to, no helper. I regret my life. I cried throughout the pregnancy until I gave birth. I am not proud of being a mother. If I see a job, I will drop her for my mother. But no job..*

For participant TMAO9, there is no support base having lost her mother before her pregnancy. The psychology of rejection was heightened by her father's decision to send her to the village in Ondo State, probably to her grandma. So she was far away from those that could give psychological, emotional and financial support to her. From pregnancy to delivery, even to nurturing of the baby up to two years, she has bore the challenges all alone. Obviously TMAO9 lacks sex and reproductive education on the one hand and social, emotional and which was largely responsible for the pregnancy, her regret, frustration, loss of self-esteem, emotional pain and lack of social and financial support.

TMAO10: *I didn't go to school. I was learning handwork hairdressing, so the boy impregnated me but refused to marry me. My parents told me to go and look for him. Even now, they have given me time to make come or they will send me out to go and look for him. My parent said eni ti a nbo, ki bo aja. (that is a dependant do not suppose to own a dog or someone being fed cannot be feeding*

a dog. This means they cannot be feeding me and my boy. Well I hope to do freedom some day, and buy equipment, if I have the money. No hope, no helper. See the boy now, I don't know what will become of him. He doesn't know his father. Can I train him alone?

Participant TMAO10 is uneducated, frustrated, abandoned, rejected, lacks emotional, psychological, social and financial supports. This participant is desperate because the parents have given her an ultimatum to locate the father of the boy or quit the house. She is hopelessness and helplessness for the teen mother and child. Although she is not educated, no disruption in her education, however, as hairdressing apprentice, there is no hope of equipping herself for future empowerment and self-sufficiency. The pressure of having to quit the house makes her more vulnerable to future sexual assault by elderly men who are able to meet her socio-economic and emotional needs.

TMAO11: *I ran away from home and my parents have relocated from the house we were living in Ketu then. So the boy promised to be my father, and everything to me. After pregnancy, he chased me out of the house. That woman is just my guidance, we met in the hospital where I delivered the baby. She was the one that gathered people to pay for my delivery. I did not finish primary school. I will learn work when my baby is old because there is no helper to send him to school.*

Participant TMAO11's challenges are multifarious and complicated as an uneducated teen lacking in parental care. Frustration, emotional distress, loneliness, disappointment, abandonment and poverty are the hallmarks of TMAO11. Perhaps the most pressing needs socio-economic and emotional support for her as a teen mother and her little child who must be well taken care of and sent to school. These are needs that look impossible because of the lack of support from parents, siblings and government.

Challenges of Teenage Motherhood: Solutions in a Digital Environment

Teenage motherhood is a global phenomenon. It is prevalent in both developed and less developed nations of the world. However, the difference is that in developed countries, teenage mothers have access to technology, loans and support, therefore, the psychological impact is cushioned compared to less developed countries. As shown in this study, a lot of pregnant girls with android phones or access to technology and digital services were able to access help, online support from human rights organizations, philanthropists, some who paid delivery bills and re-integrated them to the society. Some got sponsored to learn one trade, skill or the other in the process of re-orientating them and returning them to school. Some receive social support via numerous empowerment programmes advertised on the internet or by government agencies. The results suggested indications of psychological distress during the nursing period for all of them. These included experiences of symptoms associated with anxiety and insomnia, social isolation and severe depression. From the findings, it was discovered the teenage mothers encounter challenges from pregnancy. First, a lot of teenage mothers were not even aware that they were already pregnant. This is as a result of poor or complete lack of sex and reproductive education. They lack the knowledge of contraceptive that could prevent such unwanted pregnancy. As a matter of fact, their reaction was that of shock and disbelief, so it takes some time for the reality to dawn on them. This ignorance was found to be prevalent among the uneducated teenage mothers, some of whom got to know through the friends they confided in. It was discovered that such ignorance was not found among the fairly educated mothers among the twenty five participants selected for study.

Another challenge was fear of the unknown. Virtually all the participants experienced that initial fear of what their parents' reaction would be, fear of carrying the baby for nine months, fear of delivery and other social and economic challenges that go with pregnancy and motherhood. However, those who had access to digital services were able to be forward looking by accessing online support and skill acquisition through the internet. For instance, TMAO1 received information about entrepreneurial empowerment programme which helped to refocus her life after the disruption of her education and the attendant hopelessness. The same with TMAO2 who learnt headgear tying, “gele” online training which was already yielding result six months into apprenticeship. She says, *I already have clients who will call for home service and some people who know me in my neighborhood also patronize me. I will be alright.*

Many of the participants dropped out of school with little hope of re-entry and continuation of their education. The moment the pregnancy is visible, teen pregnant girls usually quit their education and for all the participant, only two(2) promised to go back to school. Disruption of school is the first negative consequences of teenage motherhood even though there is not a written law as far as Lagos and Ogun states are concerned the fate of teenage pregnancy and motherhood, and the prospect of re-entry to school. In an interview with an education expert, Dr. Olaogun, of Lagos State University of Education, Ota Ijanikin, there is no such law in the statute books. He says “we once had a situation where two siblings impregnated themselves and the school said they would not write WAEC. Some NGOs and concerned Nigerians went to court. They discovered there was no law that says they should be expelled. However, the two of them were prevented ultimately from writing WAEC that year on morality ground (incest), so they don’t corrupt others.” It was also discovered that a lot of teenage mothers who participated in the study have access to the social media. Therefore, those who have access to digital services like the social media, Instagram, Whatsapp were able to access help online to equip themselves preparatory to returning to school. There are online tutorial lessons that could help teenage mother pick the pieces of their lives and continue with their education. National Open University of Nigeria(NOUN) is an online university that teenage mothers can access after weaning their babies.

Common to ten(10) out of the eleven(11) participants that volunteered useful information is the issue of depression, caused by abandonment by loved ones especially parents and the escapist fathers. These challenges have been known to lead to contemplation of abortion, suicide, insomnia, diminishing self-esteem, frustration and emotional distress. However, those who have access to technology were able to weather the storm. Some of them got help from Non-governmental organizations, philanthropists and good spirited Nigerians who enrolled them for entrepreneurship training either online or physical. As a result, some of them were able to attain self-sufficiency and equip themselves in a way to be able to take care of themselves and their babies.

Again, the study discovered that all the teenage mothers, with the exception of TMAO1, lacked social, financial and emotional supports from their parents, sisters, friends and the fathers of their babies. The teenage mothers were rejected and abandoned to themselves. The pain of pregnancy and trauma of motherhood were bore by them alone, with no one to share their thought or emotion with. Some of them could not even pay for their delivery not talk of getting job to feed themselves and their babies. Poverty, lack of job, financial incapacitation and sickness characterized their lives as teenage mothers who have lost the support of their parents and escapist husbands. However, it was discovered that teenage mothers who had access to digital services were able to take care of themselves and their babies. Online empowerment skill acquisition came to the rescue to re-direct their already shattered lives and give hope to the hopeless.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Teenage motherhood as a global phenomenon is more prevalent in underdeveloped countries of the world due largely to poverty, paucity of sex and reproductive education and negative education policy that expel the pregnant teenage girl but allows the father to continue his education. Teenage motherhood comes with a lot of social, psychological and emotional trauma such as depression, insomnia, diminishing self-esteem, abortion and ultimately attempted suicide. The study contends that more sex and reproductive education must be encouraged in both primary and secondary levels of education. Government and Non-governmental Organizations must be awake to their responsibilities by providing necessary socio-economic support for the teenage mother such that will guarantee her re-entry and continuation of her education. Online programmes, training and entrepreneurial skills must be activated in all local governments and education districts in Lagos State where teenage mothers can access help. Computer training, computer programming and provision of digital services must be provided freely for teenage mothers to be self-sufficient and less dependent on their parents. Government at local level should be directly involved in the affairs of the teenage mother from pregnancy to antenatal, to delivery and nurturing of the baby. Finally, a clear cut legislation must be put in place and made public that defines the fate of the teenage mother in a way that will guarantee re-entry and continuation of her education.

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